

Re: Response of the Council for British Archaeology, Chartered Institute for Archaeologists, Federation of Archaeological Managers and Employers, and University Archaeology UK to the April 2025 Supreme Court Ruling and EHRC interim guidance update

Dear

Neil Redfern - Council for British Archaeology Executive Director and Company Secretary

Alex Llewellyn and Kate Geary - Chartered Institute for Archaeologists Interim co-CEOs

Kenneth Aitchison - Federation of Archaeological Managers and Employers Chief Executive

Vicki Cummings, Andrew Gardner, and Laura Basell - University Archaeology UK Co-Chairs

Trans people in the UK are currently facing a sustained assault by their government; an assault that threatens the ability of trans people to live in this country free from harassment, prejudice, and discrimination. This assault already undermines the ability of many archaeologists in the UK, including Council for British Archaeology (CBA), Chartered Institute for Archaeologists (CIfA), Federation of Archaeological Managers and Employers (FAME), and University Archaeology UK (UAUK) members, to work, learn, and participate in public life. Following the recent Supreme Court ruling, and the UK Equality and Human Rights Commission's (EHRC) interim update, this is only set to get worse. [Trans people have made their concerns on this matter abundantly clear](#). As signatories to this letter, some of us know what this ruling will do to the trans community first hand, and our allies know that now is the time to listen to trans people and proudly stand in solidarity. We are writing to you as academics, researchers, and archaeologists involved in UK archaeology in its broadest sense to request that you write, with urgency, on behalf of your organisations to the UK Government, the UK EHRC, commercial archaeology companies, and institutions of higher education across the UK to demand resolute inclusivity, safety, and dignity for trans, non-binary, and other gender diverse individuals within archaeology and the UK more broadly.

The Supreme Court Ruling ([For Women Scotland v The Scottish Ministers](#)), dated 16 April 2025, defined sex as it pertains to the Equality Act (2010) as 'biological sex' or the "sex as initially recorded on one's birth certificate"; a problematic over-simplification which has already [been condemned by the British Medical Association](#) (BMA). Moreover, during the proceedings, [the Supreme Court consulted no transgender organisations or individuals](#), hearing evidence *only* from pressure groups who seek to remove the rights of trans people. Despite all these flaws, which bring into question the integrity of their ruling, the Supreme Court's statement on sex as it relates to the Equality Act (2010) **[still does not mandate trans exclusion as interpreted by the EHRC](#)**. The EHRC interim guidance over-steps the law.

The EHRC's [interim guidance update](#), dated 25 April 2025, argues that work places and services open to the public should not permit trans, non-binary, or other gender diverse people to use "single-sex" facilities related to their gender. Moreover, it argues that the law allows trans people to also be prohibited from using "single-sex" facilities according to the sex they were assigned at birth. This guidance destroys the legal right for trans people to access spaces they have always used without incident and fundamentally [undermines their human rights](#). Further, by claiming that "in some circumstances" trans people should additionally be excluded from even the "single-sex" spaces associated with their sex as recorded at birth, the EHRC's interim update effectively calls for [the segregation of trans people in public life](#). We note that the UK supreme court's ruling is [already being challenged](#) in the European Court of Human Rights on these grounds.

Archaeological research has demonstrated again and again that neither gender nor sex is as simplistic and binary as the Court and EHRC assert, and that they are subject to both intra- and inter-cultural variation.¹ As signatories to this open letter, we assert that it is the responsibility of archaeological practitioners to use our expertise to speak out in defence of social justice, especially when incorrect normative assumptions are used to attack LGBTQIA+ rights.² As signatories to this letter, we request that the CBA, ClfA, FAME, and UAUUK do so, too – both for their trans and gender diverse members and the broader trans community.

Between 1-5% of UK Archaeologists are trans.³ Moreover, in the 2022 *Council for British Archaeology Youth Voice Consultation*, 5% of respondents described their gender in ways other than cisgender.⁴ It is imperative that these individuals know that their profession, discipline, and vocation stands in solidarity with them. Studies have clearly shown the extensive damage a lack of support and recognition causes trans people, up to and including highly elevated levels of suicidality.⁵ Archaeology cannot abandon its trans members, nor the trans community in broader society.

The EHRC interim update poses a grave danger to trans people in this country and, if it is implemented by institutions, it will cause extensive harm to the trans community, further exacerbating the existing inequalities faced by trans, non-binary, and gender diverse people in this country. These inequalities already manifest in archaeology, with trans archaeologists reporting higher-than-average rates of harassment.⁶ If enacted, it would establish the legitimised exclusion of trans people from public life and contribute to the ongoing mental health crisis within the community. Since the Supreme Court's ruling we have witnessed a further normalisation of transphobia, with the [Prime Minister himself declaring that trans women aren't women and that trans men aren't men](#). This mainstreaming of transphobia is alarming and deeply distressing. We must stand up against it with a resolute condemnation of the EHRC's interim guidance and organised transphobia⁷ more broadly.

We therefore ask the CBA, ClfA, FAME, and UAUUK to write to the UK Government and EHRC as soon as possible to:

- Demonstrate that archaeological evidence clearly refutes a simplistic binary view of both gender *and* sex and therefore the Supreme Court ruling is not grounded in reality; that trans men are men, trans women are women, and that non-binary people are non-binary.
- Demand that trans, non-binary, and gender diverse individuals be consulted, involved and, most importantly, listened to during the [EHRC's two week consultation period](#) for its forthcoming non-interim permanent guidance.
- State that the EHRC's interpretation of the Supreme Court Ruling, as demonstrated by its interim update, is not only incorrect, but would have a devastating impact on the UK trans community.

In addition, we request the following:

- The CBA, ClfA, FAME, and UAUUK release statements publicly condemning the Supreme Court's ruling as contrary to both the archaeological record and lived reality of past and present people; that trans men are men, that trans women are women, and that non-binary people are non-binary.
- Contact higher education institutions and archaeological companies in the UK to encourage the protection of the rights and dignities of trans staff, students, and the broader community, in workplaces and public spaces.

- Use your organisation's platform to ensure the safety and equality of trans archaeologists working in the UK. Provide resources on trans inclusion to your members and to archaeological projects taking place in the UK. This includes making sure that facilities like toilets/changing rooms/drying rooms are inclusive for trans people. Ensure that anti-trans rhetoric is stamped down, in your organisations, contracted partners, and on any sites archaeologists work at.
- Use your organisation's platform to advocate that public bodies involved in UK archaeology do not move ahead with the EHRC's interim guidance.

It is crucial at this moment that trans people, and the general public, can see how organisations and individuals are resisting this relentless advance of transphobia. It is vital that other public bodies are given the confidence to stand in solidarity with the trans community by seeing large organisations standing united against the EHRC's discriminatory guidance. We sign this letter because we are trans and/or non-binary, because we are allies who care about basic human rights in this country, and because we are archaeologists and the EHRC and Supreme Court are sabotaging and directly undermining our work, our field, and the safety of all of us. We therefore ask that the CBA, ClfA, FAME, and UAUK undertake the actions requested above to demonstrate, in no uncertain terms, their support for the trans community.

Yours sincerely,

1. Mx Owen Hurcum, AHRC (WRoCAH) and Leverhulme Trust funded PhD Candidate, Department of Archaeology, University of York
2. Dr Liz M. Quinlan, Postdoctoral Research Fellow, University of York; University of Exeter
3. Ms Claire Boardman, Researcher, University of York
4. Ms Lillian Green, Postgraduate Researcher, Department of Archaeology, University of York
5. Ms Louise Calf, Postgraduate Researcher and Research Assistant, Department of Archaeology, University of York; University of Exeter
6. Miss Nura, PhD Candidate in Archaeology, University of York
7. Miss Melissa Thomas, PhD Researcher, Department of Archaeology, University of York
8. Mr Kameron Kashani, MPhil/PhD Research Student, University College London - Institute of Archaeology
9. Professor John Schofield, Professor of Archaeology, Department of Archaeology, University of York
10. Mx Elias Michaut, AHRC Funded PhD Student, University College London
11. Mx Sylvia Lingham, Senior Archaeologist, Wardell Armstrong
12. Mrs Kate, Archaeobotanist, Wessex Archaeology
13. Mr Dylan Sorbi-Anastasi, Field Archaeologist, University College London
14. Miss Beca Davies, Archaeologist, University College London
15. Miss Anna den Hollander, PhD Candidate, Institute of Archaeology, University College London

16. Professor Penny Bickle, Professor of Funerary Archaeology, Department of Archaeology, University of York
17. Ms Lucy Moore, Curator, University of Leeds
18. Ms Yu-Chun Kan, PhD Candidate in Archaeobotany, Institute of Archaeology, University College London
19. Dr Alex Fitzpatrick, Collections Developer, University of Liverpool
20. Dr Hayley Saul, Senior Research Fellow, Deputy Director, Heritage for Global Challenges Research Centre, Department of Archaeology, University of York
21. Professor Emma Waterton, Leverhulme International Professor in Heritage Studies, Department of Archaeology, University of York
22. Dr Guillermo Diaz de Liano del Valle, Postdoctoral Research Associate, Museum of London Archaeology
23. Miss Francesca Glanville-Wallis, PhD Candidate in Archaeology, University College London
24. Miss Hayley Parsons, Field Archaeologist, ASE
25. Ms Heather Stewart Ford, PhD Researcher and Graduate Teaching Assistant, University of Glasgow
26. Miss Elizabeth Robertson, PhD Researcher, University of Glasgow
27. Ms Raven Todd DaSilva, Archaeological Communicator, Independent
28. Miss Ayelen Delgado Orellana, PhD Candidate, Institute of Archaeology, University College London
29. Miss Jodie Haggerty-Howard, Supervisor, Archaeology South East UCL
30. Dr Laurence Maidment-Blundell, Heritage Researcher, University College London
31. Mr David Stapley, PhD Researcher, Department of Archaeology, University of York
32. Dr Paul Graves-Brown, Research Associate, Department of Archaeology, University of York
33. Assistant Professor Catherine Frieman, Lecturer, ANU
34. Miss Annabel Gee, PhD Candidate, University College London
35. Dr Caitlin Kitchener, Lecturer in Historical Archaeology, University of York
36. Ms Samara King, Post-excavation Project Manager, University College London - Archaeology South-East
37. Miss Isobel Harvey, PhD Student, University of Glasgow
38. Dr Colleen Morgan, Senior Lecturer, Department of Archaeology, University of York
39. Dr Peter Schauer, Associate Lecturer, Department of Archaeology, University of York
40. Dr. Lizzie Wright, Marie Skłodowska-Curie Fellow, Department of Archaeology, University of York

41. Mr. Kyle Lewis Jordan, Archaeologist and Curator, Freelance, UCL Institute of Archaeology alum.
42. Dr Joana Valdez-Tullett, Technical Specialist / Teacher in Digital Archaeology, Wessex Archaeology / Durham University
43. Mr Peter Reavill, Herefordshire's HER officer, Herefordshire Council, Member of Institute for Archaeologists
44. Dr Clare Burke, Postdoctoral research fellow, Dept. Of Archaeology, University of York
45. Dr Gabriel Moshenska, Associate Professor, UCL Institute of Archaeology
46. Mr Chris Kolonko-Weet, Archaeologist, Archaeology Supervisor, Freelance specialist
47. Dr Patrick Randolph-Quinney, Associate Professor in Osteoarchaeology, University of Uppsala, Sweden
48. Miss Pippa Postgate, PhD Researcher, Department of Archaeology, Durham University
49. Dr Ulla Rajala, Researcher, Stockholm University (Living in Leicester)
50. Dr Rob Barratt, Lecturer in Prehistoric Archaeology, Queen's University Belfast
51. Dr Susanne Hakenback, Associate Professor, University of Cambridge
52. Mr Adam Cheshire, Digital Illustrator, Archaeology South East (UCL)
53. Ms Elise Unwin, PhD Student, Cardiff University
54. Mr K. Beachus, Principal Archaeologist Rtd, Retired
55. Miss Freya O'Dea, Masters Student of Forensics Archaeology and Anthropology, Cranfield University
56. Mr Israel, Field Archaeologist, UCL
57. Professor Abigail Hunt, Professor, Nottingham Business School, University of Nottingham
58. Mr Fran Mahon, PhD Researcher, University of York
59. Dr Tanja Hoffmann, Research Fellow, Leverhulme Heritage for Global Challenges Research Centre, University of York
60. Ms Elodie Powell, Field Project Supervisor, Oxford Archaeology
61. Ms Elisabeth Jeffries, Assistant Supervisor - Field/Training Coordinator, Oxford Archaeology Cambridge
62. Professor Hannah Cobb, Professor of Archaeology and Pedagogy, Department of Classics, Ancient History, Archaeology and Egyptology, University of Manchester
63. Mr Aplphaeus Lien-Talks, PhD Researcher, University of York, Historic England, Archaeology Data Service
64. Ms Lena Strid, Zooarchaeologist, Independent Researcher
65. Dr Fran Allfrey, Research Associate, Department of Archaeology, University of York

66. Dr Dorothy Graves McEwan, Senior Archaeology and Heritage Consultant, JBA Consulting
67. Professor John Robb, Professor, Department of Archaeology, University of Cambridge
68. Dr Jonathon Gardner, Chancellor's Fellow in Archaeology, History, Classics & Archaeology, University of Edinburgh
69. Dr Matt Pope, Associate Professor, University College London Institute of Archaeology
70. Mr Jason Steward, Senior Geoarchaeological Consultant, RSK ADAS Limited
71. Dr Kate Spence, Senior Lecturer, Department of Archaeology, University of Cambridge
72. Councillor Martin Petchy MIfA, Retired Archaeological Consultant
73. Ms Nysa Loudon, PhD Researcher in Archaeology, University of Glasgow
74. Mr Theodore Muscillo, Finds Liaison Officer, Lancashire County Council
75. Mr Bill Moffat, Operations Manager, Wessex Archaeology
76. Carmen Chulvi Escribà, PhD Student, Visiting Researcher in Archaeotonatica, University College London
77. Ms Elizabeth Hicks, PhD Researcher, Department of Archaeology, University of York
78. Dr Chloe Duckworth, Lecturer, Newcastle University
79. Mr Marcus Abbott, Freelance Archaeologist, Self Employed
80. Miss Morwenna Potter, PhD Researcher, Department of Archaeology, University of York
81. Dr Katy Whitaker, Aerial Survey Investigator, Historic England
82. Ms Jo Jones, Field Archaeologist, MOLA
83. Ms Lu Stanton-Greenwood, Data Engineering Manager, BAJR
84. Mr Thomas Houghton, Geometrics Surveyor, Oxford Archaeology
85. Mrs Ines De Almeida Carne, Archaeological Fieldwork Project Officer, Oxford Archaeology
86. Dr Lauren McIntyre, Osteoarchaeologist, Oxford Archaeology
87. Mr Sam Hogarth, Assistant Supervisor, Oxford Archaeology
88. Dr Rona Booth, Field Supervisor, Oxford Archaeology
89. Mr Lewis Ernest, Supervisor Field Archaeologist, Oxford Archaeology
90. Ms Helen Phillips, Archaeological Illustrator, Wardell Armstrong
91. Mr Edward Worsley, Supervisor, Oxford Archaeology
92. Dr Rachel Pope FSA, Reader in European Prehistory, University of Liverpool
93. Jim Harris, Field Archaeologist, Oxford Archaeology
94. Mr Edward Baker, Assistant Supervisor, Oxford Archaeology
95. Ms Naomi, Assistant Supervisor Archaeologist, Oxford Archaeology

96. Mr John Boothroyd, Senior Project Officer, Oxford Archaeology
97. Dr David Kay, Geoarchaeology Project Officer, Oxford Archaeology
98. Mr Jake Clarke, Field Archaeologist, Oxford Archaeology
99. Mr James Green, Field Archaeologist (Supervisor), Oxford Archaeology
100. Miss Lauren Carpenter, Field Archaeologist, Oxford Archaeology
101. Ms Rayli Martin-Jones, Senior Project Officer, Cotswold Archaeology
102. Dr Sadie Watson, Research Fellow, MOLA
103. Mr Aidan Farnan, Geomatics Supervisor, Oxford Archaeology
104. Mr James Fish, Supervisor, Oxford Archaeology
105. Mr Thomas Bruce, Geoarchaeologist, Oxford Archaeology
106. Dr Eva Mol, Lecturer in Roman Archaeology, Department of Archaeology, University of York
107. Miss Katherine Bradshaw, Project Supervisor, York Archaeology
108. Ms Carmen Dahlke, Field Archaeologist, York Archaeology
109. Dr Harald Fredheim, Lecturer in Museum Studies, Department of Archaeology, University of York
110. Mr James Badger, Post Excavation Officer, York Archaeology
111. Mr Paul Durdin, Freelance Archaeologist
112. Mr Benjamin Rudd, Graduate of BA Archaeology, Former Project Supervisor, University of York
113. Dr Hannah B Page, Research Fellow, University of Padova, alum. UCL Institute of Archaeology
114. Dr Rachel Crellin, Associate Professor of Archaeology, University of Leicester
115. Miss Charlotte Lucy Molloy, Research Scientist (Archaeobotany) PCIFA, UCD
116. Mr Ted Levermore, Post-Excavation Archaeologist, Oxford Archaeology
117. Ms Anne Stewardson, Illustrator, Oxford Archaeology
118. Mr Cain Redmayne, Field Archaeologist, Oxford Archaeology
119. Mrs Laura Desrosiers-Whalley, Field Archaeologist (Project Officer, Lithic Specialist) Pre-Construct Archaeology (University of York alum.)
120. Mr Johann Lemee, Field Archaeologist, Humber Field Archaeology
121. Miss Enya Horton, Assistant Supervisor, MAP Archaeological Practice
122. Rachel Glaves, MAP Archaeological Practice
123. Mr Ben Attfield, Fieldwork Supervisor, Oxford Archaeology

124. Miss Sîan, Find Manager, PCA
125. Dr Enrico Crema, Associate Professor, Department of Archaeology, University of Cambridge
126. Ms Charlotte Taplin, Assistant Supervisor, Oxford Archaeology
127. Miss Emily Knight, Field Archaeologist, Oxford Archaeology
128. Dr Stephan O'Brien, Archaeologist, Self Employed
129. Ms Matilda Little, Field Archaeologist, Pre-Construct Archaeology Ltd
130. Mr William Taylor
131. Miss Niamh Malone, PhD Student, University of York
132. Mrs Nicola Gifford Cowan, Operations Manager, Oxford Archaeology Ltd.
133. Mr James Smalley, Assistance Supervisor, Field Archaeologist, Oxford Archaeology
134. Miss Sophia Newton, Assistant Supervisor, Oxford Archaeology
135. Dr Beatrijs de Groot, Teaching Fellow in European Archaeology, University of Edinburgh
136. Dr Lucy Koster, Committee Member/Human Remains Team, Sedgeford Historical and Archaeological Research Project
137. Mr David Connolly, Director, British Archaeological Jobs Resource BAJR
138. Mrs Alison James, Director, MSDS Marine
139. Miss Evelyn Pearce, Cleaner (ex- supervisor), University of Leicester
140. Ms Sue McGalliard, Senior Cultural Heritage Consultant, WSP
141. Mr Jack Rowe, PhD Student, University of Bradford
142. Miss Jessica Latham, Communications and Marketing Manager, Council for British Archaeology
143. Dr Hannah Fluck, Senior National Archaeologist, National Trust
144. Dr Tansy Branscombe, Editor, BAR Publishing
145. Miss Cat Lodge, Archaeologist, National Trust
146. Ms. Gabrielle Faig, Marketing and Operations Assistant, BAR Publishing
147. Ms Ali Cameron, Director, Cameron Archaeology
148. Mrs Katherine Toms, Digital Content Manager, University of York
149. Mr Dan Barrett, Archaeologist, Barrett Archaeology
150. Mx Charlie Robertson, Osteoarchaeologist, Wessex Archaeology
151. Miss Natalie Williams, Field Archaeologist, Border Archaeology
152. Miss Katrina Gargett, Audience and Network Manager, Council for British Archaeology

153. Ms Andrea Hamel, Project Manager, Wessex Archaeology
154. Ms Jill Hummerstone, Tutor in Archaeology, City Literary Institute
155. Dr Domiziana Rossi, Senior Archaeologist, AECOM
156. Dr Hannah Cutler, Archaeological Officer, Suffolk County Council Archaeological Service
157. Mrs Jenny Emmett, Senior Planning Archaeologist, Heneb - The Trust for Welsh Archaeology
158. Mr Ben Saunders, Marine Archaeologist, Wessex Archaeology
159. Dr James Taylor, Lecturer in Field Archaeology and Digital Methods, University of York
160. Ms Helen Ashworth, Research Manager, Heritage Network
161. Miss Hannah Rai Munns, Apprentice Project Archaeologist, Cirencester College
162. Holly Newman, Student, Cambridge
163. Mr Luke Smith, Apprentice Archaeological Assistant, Cirencester College
164. Ms Sefryn Penrose, Director, ButCH (Bureau for the Contemporary and Historic)
165. Ms Raffi Williamson, Field Archaeology Apprentice, Archaeology South East
166. Dr Sarah May, Co-Director, ButCH (Bureau for the Contemporary and Historic)
167. Mrs Catherine Whitehouse, Archaeological Consultant, AtkinsRealis
168. Professor Oliver Harris, Professor of Archaeology, University of Leicester
169. Mr Stefan Sagrott, Senior Lecturer in Classical Archaeology, University of Winchester
170. Dr Katy Soar, Senior Lecturer in Classical Archaeology, University of Winchester
171. Miss Adelina Teoaca, Finds and Archive Manager, Canterbury Archaeological Trust
172. Ms Robin Searle, Environmental Assistant Supervisor, Oxford Archaeology
173. Ms Kat Hopwood-Lewis, Senior Peatland Historic Environment Officer
174. Alison Atkin, BA, MSc, Creative Content Producer (Heritage)
175. Ms Cat Rees, PhD, Amgueddfa Cymru and Manchester Metropolitan University
176. Mx Mrinalini Venugopal, Postgraduate Researcher, Glasgow Caledonian University
177. Ms K Hawkins, Senior Archaeologist, UCL Institute of Archaeology
178. Dr Kimm Curran, Field School - Heritage Lead, University of Glasgow
179. Mr Chris Martin-Taylor, Field Archaeologist and Project Officer, KDK Archaeology
180. Ms Agnes Kener, Archaeologist, Rathmell Archaeology
181. Dr Pen Foreman, Chair, Board EDI Champion, ClfA
182. Dr Tess Machling, Researcher, Independent

183. Dr D.M.J Seal, Researcher, Independent Scholar
184. Dr Zena Kamash, Senior Researcher, KCL
185. Ms Jacky Sommerville, Senior Finds Officer, Cotswold Archaeology
186. Mrs Clare Jackson-Slater, Report Writer and Researcher, Wessex Archaeology
187. Dr Fiona Coward, Associate Professor in Archaeological Science, Department of Archaeology & Anthropology, Bournemouth University
188. Dr Josie Wall, Archaeologist, Independent Scholar
189. Mrs Liz Mordue, Planning Archaeologist, North Northants Council
190. Miss Emilie Green, PhD Student, University of Aberdeen
191. Miss Anna Vekony, PhD Researcher, University of Southampton
192. Miss Charlotte Howley, PhD Candidate, Iranian Archaeology and Philology, University of California, Los Angeles (Formerly University of Oxford)
193. Ms Lucy Beasley, Student Archaeologist, University of Oxford
194. Mg Clara de Sousa Cunha, Finds Liaison Officer, Portable Antiquities Scheme, Birmingham Museums Trust
195. Ms Iseabail Wilks, Postgraduate Researcher, Department of Archaeology, University of York
196. Miss Sarah Williams, Finds Liaison Assistant, Birmingham Museums Trust/Portable Antiquities Scheme
197. Miss Kate Potter-Farrant, Curatorial and Archaeological Finds Arts Scholar, Birmingham Museums Trust
198. Ms Jet Jansen, Project Supervisor, Cotswold Archaeology
199. Mx Kostja Junglas, PhD Student in Archaeological Sciences, University of Oxford, School of Archaeology
200. Alice Dowsett, Geoarchaeologist, Archaeology South-East (UCL)
201. Mrs Alexandra Taylor Redish, Post Excavation and Archival Assistant, Cornwall Archaeological Unit
202. Dr Orla Craig, Ancient Monuments Officer, Historic Environment Scotland
203. Dr Richard Nevell, Honorary Research Fellow, Archaeology Department, University of Exeter
204. Mr James Bonnor, Senior Archaeological Consultant, Prospect Archaeology
205. Mr Tristan Boyle, Co-Founder, Archaeology Podcast Network
206. Miss Ella Appleyard, Post-Excavation Archaeologist, University College London (Archaeology South-East)

207. Mr Tom Watson, Archaeological Illustrator, Headland Archaeology
208. Mr Matthew J. Lee, Durham Doctoral Scheme Funded PhD student (1) and EDI Trustee (2), (1) Durham University and (2) British Association for Biological Anthropology and Osteoarchaeology
209. Dr Stephen J Maclean, Senior Lecturer in Archaeology, Edinburgh Medical School, University of Edinburgh
210. Mx Taylor Peacock, Doctoral Student in Archaeology, University of Cambridge
211. Mx Forest Bird, MSc Forensic Archaeology and Anthropology Student, Cranfield University
212. Dr Rebecca M. Wragg Sykes, Archaeologist, Author, Public Scholar, Honorary Research Associate, University of Cambridge; Honorary Fellow, University of Liverpool
213. Miss Olivia Arkley, PhD Candidate, Department of Archaeology, University of Liverpool
214. Miss Amy Rattenbury, Senior Lecturer, Applied Science, Wrexham University
215. Ms April Williams, Archaeology and Heritage Consultant, Stantec
216. Miss Fiona Eaglesham, Environmental Archaeologist, Wessex Archaeology
217. Ms Jasmine Porter, Archaeologist, Yorkshire
218. Miss Isobel Christian, Historic Environment Researcher, Wessex Archaeology
219. Dr Tom Gardner, Senior Ancient Monuments Officer, Historic Environment Scotland
220. Mx Aster Wood, PhD Researcher, Department of Archaeology, University of York
221. Ms Alex Rodzinka, PhD Candidate in Archaeology, Cranfield University
222. Dr Ian McAfee, Field Archaeologist, University of Sheffield
223. Mr Rory Calvert, Field Archaeologist, Cotswold Archaeology
224. Dr Anna Collar, Associate Professor of Archaeology, University of Southampton
225. Ms Roberta Marziani, Senior Surveyor, Wessex Archaeology
226. Miss Georgina Fowles, PhD Researcher in Medieval Studies, Centre for Medieval Studies, University of York
227. Dr Jo Buckberry, Reader in Biological Anthropology, School for Archaeological and Forensic Sciences, University of Bradford
228. Ms Clare King, Principal Consultant, Wessex Archaeology
229. Miss Hayley Nicholls, Project Officer, Archaeology South-East (UCL)
230. Mr Craig Stewart, Cultural Heritage Consultant, WSP
231. Miss Allie Burrill, Student of Bioarchaeology, University of York
232. Mr Martyn Barber, Retired, Historic England (Retired)

233. Miss Leah Morrow, Archaeology Student, University of York
234. Mr Benjamin Massey, Project Archaeologist, Headland Archaeology
235. Dr Hanna Steyne, Technical Specialist/Honorary Research Fellow, Wessex Archaeology/University of Manchester
236. Miss Katrina Tomlinson, PhD Researcher, Department of Archaeology, Bournemouth University
237. Mx Amy Allinson MSc, Archaeological Geophysicist, SUMO Geophysics
238. Mrs Rose Hooker, Volunteer
239. Miss Ellen Durbin, Assistant Supervisor, Wessex Archaeology
240. Ms Rosie Loftus BA(Hons) ACIFA, Field Archaeologist, CFA Archaeology
241. Miss Jessi Corser, Field Archaeologist, PCA
242. Laura Mazur, Trainee Field Archaeologist, Cotswold Archaeology
243. Mr Mike Middleton, Archaeological Data Management Officer, Historic Environment Scotland
244. Miss Emma, Field Archaeologist, Oxford Archaeology
245. Mrs Catherine Stallybrass, Craftsperson
246. Miss Elise Holmes, Experienced Archaeologist, Cotswold Archaeology
247. Dr Dylan Gaffney, Associate Professor of Palaeolithic Archaeology, University of Oxford
248. Dr Craig Spence, Archaeologist & Historian, Independent Researcher
249. Mr Ben Carrick, Fieldwork Archaeologist, Cotswold Archaeology
250. Mr Mark James, Operations and Technical Director, MSDS Marine
251. Dr Amanda Wintcher, Field Archaeologist, Self-Employed
252. Mr John Strachan, Trainee Archaeologist, GUARD Archaeology Ltd
253. Dr Ellen Green, Osteoarchaeologist, AOC Archaeology
254. Mrs Jess Butt, Student and Finds Assistant, University of Leicester and CBAS
255. Mr Arran Johnson, Archaeologist, Independent
256. Ms Morgan Adams, Project Assistant Osteologist, London Museum
257. Mr Leon, MSc Student, University of York
258. Grace Caroll, Archaeology Student, University of York
259. Miss Madeline Steinsultz, Archaeology Student, University of York
260. Miss Devon McLean, Postgraduate Student, University of York
261. Miss Amy McKee, Archive Assistant, Gateshead Council Archive

262. Mx Gemma Deaney, Field Archaeologist, Cotswold Archaeology
263. Dr David Roberts, Senior Lecturer in Roman Archaeology and History, Cardiff University
264. Dr Robert Brian Rahn, Researcher, Independent
265. Miss Jelena Bekvalac, Curator of Human Osteology, London Museum
266. Mr Keith Fitzpatrick-Matthews, Museum Curator, North Hertfordshire Museum
267. Mr Mark Knight, Senior Project Officer, Cambridge Archaeological Unit, University of Cambridge
268. Ms Emma Boast MA, Archaeological Find and Archives Technician, University of York
269. Ms Kira Chatterjee, Postgraduate Student, University of York
270. Mx Isobel Skemp, Archaeologist, Oxford Archaeology
271. Mx Catherine Maskrey, Unemployed
272. Professor Terry O'Connor, Emeritus Professor of Archaeological Science, Department of Archaeology, University of York
273. Mr Henry Moore, Field Archaeologist, Pre Construct Archaeology
274. Professor Dan Lawrence, Professor, Durham University
275. Dr Hanna Moots, Archaeogeneticist, University of Cambridge Alum
276. Dr Despoina Sampatakou, Research Associate, University of Glasgow
277. Ms Claire Hayes, Field Archaeologist, Oxford Archaeology
278. Mrs Sarah Rousseau, Heritage Professional
279. Professor Sonia Zakrzewski, Professor of Bioarchaeology and Bioanthropology, University of Southampton
280. Mx Kelsey Smith, Master's Degree Holder in Archaeology, University of Aberdeen
281. Miss Rosie Hoggard, Assistant Supervisor, Oxford Archaeology
282. Mr Daniel Percy, Assistant Supervisor, Pre-Construct Archaeology
283. Miss Niamh Hobson, Archaeology Undergraduate Student, Durham University
284. Mr John J Johnston, Egyptologist and Cultural Historian, The International Society of the Study of Egyptomania,
285. Mr Oliver Goodwin, Society Member, Nautical Archaeology Society
286. Dr Rick Jones, Retired, formerly Reacer & Senior Lecture, Universities of Leeds & Bradford
287. Mx Ray Plummer, BA Archaeology Student, University of Manchester
288. Mr Adam Simpson, Field Archaeologist, Oxford Archaeology

289. Dr Rachel King, Associate Professor in Cultural Heritage Studies, UCL Institute of Archaeology
290. Ms Kelsi Kaviani, PhD Candidate, Institute of Archaeology, University College London
291. Miss Ellinor Berggren, Field Archaeologist, (Previously) Headland Archaeology
292. Dr Matt Law, Freeland Environmental Archaeologist and Senior Lecturer, Bath Spa University
293. Dr Vic Lucas, Archaeomaterials Technician, Institute of Archaeology University College London
294. Dr Catriona Cooper, Senior Lecturer, Canterbury Christ Church University
295. Dr Lesley McFadyen, Lecturer, Birkbeck, University of London
296. Miss Lauren Paddock, Project Archaeologist, York Archaeology
297. Yasmine de Gruchy, PhD Researcher, School of History, Archaeology and Religion, Cardiff University
298. Miss Freya Greaves, Archaeological Consultant, Jacobs
299. Dr T.A. Husøy, Historian, Norwegian Church
300. Mr David Etheridge, Programme Manager, FdA History, Heritage and Archaeology, Strode College
301. Mr Dāvis Strūbergs, Senior Assistant Project Officer, Archaeological Research Services
302. Mr Tom Parker, Archaeologist Surveyor, Magpie Surveying
303. Miss Vickki Hudson, Heritage Regeneration Project Assistant, Isle of Anglesey County Council
304. Ms Hannah Cavers, Field Archaeologist, Oxford Archaeology
305. Ms Lucie Collett, Master's Student, Archaeologist, University of Reading
306. Lucy Parker, Postgraduate Researcher, Bournemouth University
307. Ms Rebecca Devaney, Post-Excavation Project Officer (Lithics Analyst), Oxford Archaeology & Freelance
308. Dr Chris Constable, Borough Archaeologist, Southwark Council
309. Dr Kristian Strutt, Senior Teaching Fellow, Department of Archaeology, University of Southampton
310. Mx Neffian, Supervisor, Headland Archaeology Ltd
311. Miss Iseult Bell, Cornish Archaeology YouTuber, Graduate, University of Winchester
312. Dr Rebecca Aroon Enlander, Curatorial Archaeologist, Historic Environment Division Northern Ireland
313. Ms Beki Jones, Associate, Dalcour Maclaren

314. Ms Ingrid O'Donnell, PhD Candidate, Bournemouth University
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320. Miss Eirlys Walker, Field Assistant Supervisor, Oxford Archaeology
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323. Mr Jonathan Turner, Archaeological Fieldwork Supervisor, CFA Archaeology
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334. Dr Samantha Purchase, University Teaching Associate, University of Sheffield
335. Mx Ségdæe Richardson-Read, PhD Candidate, Institute of Irish Studies, University of Liverpool
336. Ms Issica Baron BA(Hons), MA, ACIfA, Project Archaeologist
337. Mrs Natasha Best, Undergraduate, School of Historical Studies, Birkbeck, University of London
338. Dr Alice Rose, Postdoctoral Research Associate, Department of Archaeology, University of York
339. Mr Lewis Busby, Archaeological Officer, Cambridgeshire County Council
340. Dr Ange Boyle, Self Employed

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342. Mr Nicholas Clarke, Geospatial Technician, University of Sheffield
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348. Dr Caroline Bennett, Assistant Professor in Anthropology and International Development (Human Rights), University of Sussex School of Global Studies
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362. Miss Skye Ennis, Field Archaeologist, Alum. University of York
363. Ms Ellie Drew, Collections and Archives Officer, York Archaeology
364. Professor Graeme Warren, Professor, University College Dublin
365. Miss Josephine Cavaliere, Field Archaeologist, Network Archaeology
366. Ms Anna Fisher, Student Archaeologist, University of Leicester
367. Mr Nathan Sleaford, Previously Commercial Field Archaeologist and Environmental Archaeologist, Alum. Universities of York and Durham
368. Miss Ashley Perkins, Alumni from the School of Ancient History and Archaeology, University of Leicester

369. Mr Garrett Sheehan, Field Archaeologist, UCL Institute of Archaeology
370. Miss Laurie Matthews, Supervisor Archaeologist, Commercial Archaeology
371. Ms Alice Holliday, Field Archaeologist, MOLA
372. Mr Joseph MacDonogh, Field Archaeology, AOC Archaeology
373. Mr Nathaniel Bidgood-Shelley, Archaeologist, University of Manchester
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375. Mx Sacha Davies, MPhil Archaeological Science Student, University of Cambridge
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395. Miss Leila Qubayba, Student Archaeologist, University of Leicester
396. Mx Mac MacFarlane, Recent Archaeology Graduate, University of Leicester

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399. Mx Nida Bhunnoo, Archaeology Graphics Technician, RPS Heritage
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405. Ms Amal Khreisheh, Senior Curator, South West Heritage Trust
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420. Mr Benjamin Allen PCifA, Archaeologist (Geophysics), AOC Archaeology, MSc Digital Archaeology Student, Department of Archaeology, University of York
421. Mr Miles Pitcher, Undergraduate Archaeology Student, University of York
422. Dr Mike Heyworth, Consultant, Heyworth Heritage
423. Nrs Rowan Reis, Field Archaeologist, Self Employed
424. Mr Harry Davies, Assistant Archaeological Supervisor CFA Archaeology
425. Mr Jamie Stuart, Field Archaeologist, York Archaeology

426. Mr Dylan Bowman-Phillips, BSc Archaeology Student, University of York
427. Mr James McCarthy, Archaeology Student, University of York
428. Dr Gianluca Foschi, Visiting Researcher, School of History, Classics and Archaeology, Newcastle University
429. Dr Hannah Russ, Director, archaeology.biz
430. Mr Christos Nikolaou, PhD Student, University of Cambridge
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489. Haley, PhD Candidate, Department of Archaeology, University of Birmingham
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511. Mr Daniel BA Historical Archaeology, University of York
512. Ms Darcie Eastham, Graduate Trainee Fieldwork, Oxford Archaeology

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514. Mrs Lucy Gane, Archaeological Illustrator, Oxford Archaeology
515. Ms Eleanor Johnson, Assistant Supervisor Field Archaeologist, Oxford Archaeology
516. Mr Ken Whittaker, Historic Environment Consultant, SCS Railways
517. Miss Hannah Pighills, Finds Supervisor/Junior Specialist, Oxford Archaeology Cambridge
518. Mr David Gilbert, Director, Rubicon Archaeology Ltd.
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540. Professor Chris Fowler, Professor of Archaeology, Newcastle University
541. Miss Ellie Chipps, PhD Student, University of Reading
542. Dr Brandon Fathy, Lecturer in Later Medieval Archaeology, School of Archaeology, Geography, and Environmental Sciences, University of Reading
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544. Miss Tess Fox, Student, Department of Archaeology, University of Reading
545. Dr Karen Ruebens, Lecturer, University of Reading
546. Ms Carina Garland, Field Archaeologist and PhD Researcher, University of Reading
547. Miss Hester Crothers, Geoarchaeologist, QUEST, University of Reading
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550. Miss Amy Campbell, Student, University of Reading
551. Miss Jenna Smith, HER Officer, Heneb - The Trust for Welsh Archaeology
552. Miss Juliette Kent, Professional Placement Student with QUEST, University of Reading
553. Ms Letty Ingrej, Senior Geoarchaeologist/PhD Student, Archaeology South-East/University of Reading
554. Ms Elizabeth Hockin, Postgraduate Archaeology Student, University of Reading
555. Dr Duncan Wright, Senior Lecturer in Medieval Archaeology, Newcastle University
556. Mr Ash Dobie, Laboratory and Fieldwork Technician, University of Reading
557. Miss Eleanor Olden, Archaeology Student, University of Reading
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560. Mr Ben Creedy, Archaeology Student, University of Reading
561. Miss Maddie Ager, Archaeologist Trainer, Cotswold Archaeology
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570. Ms Runa Wylde, Undergraduate Archaeology Student, University of Leicester
571. Miss Charlotte Gifford, Student, University of Leicester
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574. Mrs Jo Wyke, Archaeology and Ancient History Student, University of Leicester
575. Mrs Sam Hawkins, Undergraduate Student, School of Ancient History and Archaeology, University of Leicester
576. Miss A. Watts, Archaeology Undergraduate Student
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583. Ms Lily Gauthier, Field Archaeologist, University of Leicester
584. Mr William Luggar, Student and Registered Volunteer, University of Reading and Cotswold Archaeology
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586. Dr Flint Dibble, Teacher, School of History, Archaeology, and Religion, Cardiff University
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588. Mr Robert English, Archaeology Undergraduate Student, University of Leicester
589. Miss Esme Scarle, Archaeology Student, University of Leicester
590. Ms Victoria Alexander, Archivist, Rubicon Archaeology
591. Miss Courtney Barnett, Masters Student in Archaeology, University of Southampton
592. Ms Sandra Garside-Neville, CBM Specialist
593. Ms Phoebe Hughes, Undergraduate Archaeologist, University of Reading
594. Mx Xander Phillips, Archaeology Student, University of Leicester

595. Mr Eddie Watson, Part 3 Archaeology Student, University of Reading
596. Miss Holly Rallings, Student, University of Reading
597. Miss Alice Daley, Student, University of Leicester
598. Miss Charis Murray, Archaeology Student, University of Reading
599. Ms Ruby Metcalfe, Archaeology Student, University of Reading
600. Mrs Bronwen Russell, Visiting Research Fellow, Bournemouth University
601. Mr Lee Fisher, Student Archaeologist, University of Leicester
602. Miss Valentina Ruggeri, Archaeology Student, University of Reading
603. Dr Miles Russell, Director of Archaeological Fieldwork, Department of Archaeology and Anthropology, Bournemouth University
604. Ms Katherine Classey, Ancient History and Classical Archaeology Student, University of Leicester
605. Mr Samuel Hay, Archaeological Assistant, University of Leicester Archaeological Services
606. Miss Jasmin Lycett, Geoarchaeologist, Wessex Archaeology
607. Dr Susan Greaney, Lecturer, University of Exeter
608. Miss Isabelle Burgess, Student, Department of Archaeology, University of Reading
609. Mr Gabriel Smith, Archaeology Student, University of Reading
610. Dr Linus Girdland Flink, Lecturer, Department of Archaeology, University of Aberdeen
611. Dosentti Dr Eljas Oksanen, Researcher, Department of Archaeology, University of Reading
612. Professor Clare Downham, Lecturer, University of Liverpool
613. Dr Ben Elliott, Lecturer in Archaeology, Archaeology Institute, UHI
614. Miss Victoria Wilson, Project Archaeologist, University of Aberdeen
615. Mr Alexander Smith, Senior site assistant, Colchester Archaeological Trust
616. M Lara Band, Researcher, Freelance
617. Ms Eurika Bailey, Student, Department of Archaeology, University of Reading
618. Mrs Gina Little, Student, University of Leicester
619. Miss Lidia Oliver, Undergraduate archaeologist, University of Reading
620. Miss Fabienne Miles, Undergraduate, Department of Archaeology, University of Reading
621. Mr Andy Rogers, PhD Archaeology Candidate, School of Archaeology and Ancient History, University of Leicester
622. Miss Brodhie Molloy, PhD Candidate, School of Archaeology and Ancient History, University of Leicester

623. Mr Gareth Clark, Student, University of Reading
624. Mx Ashley Tuck, Research Manager, Wessex Archaeology
625. Mr Graham Taylor, Ceramic Technology Practitioner, Potted History, Independent
626. Mrs Anna Wood, Archaeology Student, University of Leicester
627. Ms Kyra Anderson, Archaeologist, Cotswold Archaeology
628. Miss Teagen
629. Miss Cassie Bradshaw, Archaeologist, Cotswold Archaeology
630. Mr Kieran Stemp, Field Archaeologist, Oxford Archaeology
631. Miss Georgina Orchard, Part 3 Undergraduate Student, Department of Archaeology, University of Reading
632. Mr Luke Roberts, Fieldwork Project Officer, Wessex Archaeology
633. Miss Juniper Little, 3rd Year Archaeology Student, University of Leicester
634. Miss Kira Chapman, Student, Department of Archaeology, Reading University
635. Miss Erin Rushforth, Field Archaeologist, Cotswold Archaeology
636. Mr Leif Stimpson, Undergraduate Student, University of Leicester
637. Miss Amy Holmes, Archaeology Undergraduate, University of Reading
638. Mr Paul Gelderd, Retired Field Archaeologist, University of Wales, Lampeter
639. Mr Miguel Fiori, Student, University of Reading
640. Mr Jack Heathcote, Field Archaeologist, Assistant Supervisor, Oxford Archaeology
641. Dr Sally Waite, Lecturer, School of History, Classics and Archaeology, Newcastle University
642. Mr Benjamin Jones, Ancient History Undergraduate Student, University of Leicester
643. Miss Ella Town, Undergraduate Student, University of Manchester
644. Ms Rebecca Smart, Senior Project Officer, Cotswold Archaeology
645. Voilette Horton-Haydock, Student, University of Leicester
646. Mrs Natalie McKittrick, Assistant Supervisor Archaeologist, CFA Archaeology
647. Ms Clemency Cooper, Community Partnership Coordinator, University of Cambridge Museums
648. Thomas Jordan, Ancient History Graduate, University of Nottingham
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650. Miss Mia Wright, Student of Archaeology and Ancient History, University of Reading
651. Miss Eva Hancock, Student, Department of Archaeology, University of Reading

652. Miss Avneet Kaur Kler, Archaeologist, University of Reading
653. Miss Elsby, NHS Worker
654. Miss Katie Greig, Assistant Supervisor, Headland Archaeology Ltd.
655. Miss Neeve Harris, Field Archaeologist
656. Mrs Jessica Irwin, Archives Manager, Wessex Archaeology
657. Mr Adam Down, Student, School of Archaeology and Ancient History, University of Leicester
658. Ms Abigail Phipp, Undergraduate Student, University of Reading
659. Miss Giselle Király, Fieldwork Project Officer, PCAS Archaeology Ltd
660. Mr Rui Oliveira, Field Archaeologist, Cotswold Archaeology
661. Miss Jesse Dawes, BA Archaeology Student, Reading University
662. Miss Beth Allport, Student, University of York
663. Miss Indigo Ridgwell, Fieldwork Supervisor, Oxford Archaeology
664. Ms Alice Jones, Associate Consultant, Savills Heritage, Townscape and Archaeology
665. Mr Kristian Chadwick, SHEQ Assistant, Cotswold Archaeology
666. Mr Liam Wilson, Project Officer, Cotswold Archaeology
667. Mr William Nicoll, MSc Digital Archaeology Student, University of York
668. Mrs Fliss Greenhead, Undergraduate Student of Ancient History and Archaeology, University of Leicester
669. Mr Daniel Firth, Fieldwork Project Officer, Oxford Archaeology
670. Dr Stelios Lekakis, Principal Research Associate, School of History, Classics and Archaeology, Newcastle University
671. Miss Chloe Cronouge-Freeman, Senior Planning Archaeologist, Leicester County Council
672. Ms Caitlin Sutherland, Archaeologist, Independent
673. Miss Eszter Balogh, Field Archaeologist, Rubicon Archaeology
674. Ms Emilia, Field Archaeologist, Oxford Archaeology
675. Miss Zoe Miles, Post-Excavation Assistant, University of Leicester Archaeological Services
676. Miss Sarah Sunman, BA Archaeology Alumni, Department of Archaeology, University of Manchester
677. Miss Molly Jenner, Archaeology Alumni, University of York
678. Dr David Walsh, Career Development Fellow, Department of Archaeology, Durham University
679. Miss Feyre Heaney, Masters Student of Roman Archaeology, University of York

680. Miss Abigail Edson, Archaeology Student, Department of Archaeology, University of York
681. Dr Francesca Romana Del Fattore, Post Doctoral Researcher (MSCA/EPSRC Fellow), Newcastle University
682. Ms Esther Jones, Treasure Registrar, Department of Archaeology & Numismatics, Amgueddfa Cymru - National Museum Wales
683. Miss Ciara Donnelly, Assistant Supervisor Field Archaeologist, Oxford Archaeology
684. Miss Georgia Smith, MA Student, Department of Archaeology, University of York
685. Miss Charlotte Nicol-Cobb, Post Excavation Assistant, Cotswold Archaeology
686. Mr Racin Abdulai Baldé Ly, PhD Candidate, University of Birmingham
687. Dr. Felicia Fricke, Postdoctoral Fellow, University of Copenhagen
688. Mr Christopher Jones, Student, Leicester University
689. Mr Gabriel Caines, Postgraduate Archaeology Student, Department of Archaeology, University of York
690. Mx Carol Hayward, Marine Geophysicist, Wessex Archaeology
691. Mr George Issitt, Archaeological Assistant (Field and Archives), University of Leicester Archaeological Services
692. Ms Amy Halliday, Project Officer, AOC Archaeology
693. Ms Catriona Martin-Lennie, Public Archaeologist (Guided Tour and Visitor Experience Manager), University of Glasgow/UCL
694. Miss Fahimah Begum, Archaeology and Anthropology Student, SAGES Reading
695. Dr Jonathan Last, Archaeologist, Historic England
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702. Mr Nate Richardson, Undergraduate Student, University of Leicester
703. Ms Julia Granato, Researcher and Collaborator, University of Oxford
704. Miss Emily Storey, Student, School of Archaeology, Geography and Environmental Science, University of Reading

Endnotes

1. For example: **BABAO (2022)**; BABAO Statement on Sex Estimation, BABAO. [Online]. Available at: <https://babao.org.uk/babao-statement-on-sex-estimation/>, **Gaydarska, B. et al. (2023)**; To Gender or not to Gender? Exploring Gender Variations through Time and Space, *European Journal of Archaeology*, 26(3), 271-298, **Moen, M. (2019)**; Gender and Archaeology: Where Are We Now?, *Archaeologies*, 15(2), 206-226, **Anastasiadou, K. et al. (2024)**; Detection of Chromosomal Aneuploidy in Ancient Genomes, *Communications Biology*, 7(1) 319–335, **Moilanen et al. (2022)**; A Woman with a Sword? – Weapon Grave at Suontaka Vesitorninmäki, Finland, *European Journal of Archaeology*, 25(1), 42-60, or **Coltofaen-Arzancu, L., Gaydarska, B. & U. Matić. (eds.) (2021)**; *Gender stereotypes in archaeology: A short reflection in image and text*. sidestonepress.
2. See: **Weismantel, M. (2013)**; Towards a Transgender Archaeology: a Queer Rampage Through Prehistory. In: S. Stryker and A. Z. Aizura (Eds.). *The Transgender Studies Reader 2*. Taylor & Francis, London & New York, **Dowson, T. (ed.) (2000)**; Queer Archaeologies, *World Archaeology*, 32(2), **Terendy, S., Lyons, N., and Janse-Smekal, M. (eds.) (2009)**; *Que(e)rying Archaeology – Proceedings of the 37th Annual Chacmool Conference*, University of Calgary, **McGuire, R. (2008)**; *Archaeology as Political Action*, University of California Press, or **Atalay, S., Clauss, L.R., McGuire, R., and Welch, J. (eds.) (2014)**; *Transforming Archaeology: Activist Practices and Prospects*, Routledge, London and New York.
3. *Profiling the Profession* and *ClfA EDI Survey* (presented at TAG 2023).
4. **Coomb, L. (2022)**; *Council for British Archaeology Youth Voice Consultation*.
5. For example: **Horton, C. (2024)**; The Cass Review: Cis-Supremacy in the UK’s approach to healthcare for trans children, *International Journal of Transgender Health*, 1-25, **Lizone, M. (2024)**; Trans Youth Suicides Covered Up By NHS, Cass After Restrictions, Say Whistleblowers, *Erin In The Morning*. [Online]. Available at: <https://www.erininthemorning.com/p/trans-youth-suicides-covered-up-by>, **Hendricks, M., and Testa, R. (2012)**. A conceptual framework for clinical work with transgender and gender nonconforming clients: An adaptation of the Minority Stress Model, *Professional Psychology: Research and Practice*, 43(5), 460-67, **Bauer, G., Hammond, R., Travers, R., Kaay, M., Hohenadel, K., and Boyce, M. (2009)**. “I don’t think this is theoretical; this is our lives”: how erasure impacts health care for transgender people, *JANAC*, 20(5), 348-361, **Pollitt, A., Ioverno, S., Russell, S., Li, G. and Grossman, H. (2021)** Predictors and Mental Health Benefits of Chosen Name Use Among Transgender Youth, *Youth & Society*, 53(2), 320-341, or **Bailey, L., Sonja, E., and McNeil, J. (2014)** Suicide Risk in the UK Trans Population and the Role of Gender Transition in Decreasing Suicidal Ideation and Suicide Attempt, *Mental Health Review Journal*, 19(4), 209-220.
6. **Voss, B. L. (2021)**; Disrupting cultures of harassment in archaeology: Social-environmental and trauma-informed approaches to disciplinary transformation. *American Antiquity*, 86(3), 447-464.
7. **Amery, F. and Mondon, A. (2024)**; Othering, peaking, populism and moral panics: The reactionary strategies of organised transphobia, *The Sociological Review*, 0(0), see also **Butler, J. (2024)** *Who’s Afraid of Gender*, Farrar, Straus and Giroux, **Faye, S. (2021)**; *The Transgender Issue*, Penguin Books, or **Lester, C.N. (2017)**; *Trans Like Me*, Virago Press.